

EVALUATION OF AN ANALYTICAL APPROACH PREDICTING THE TRANSVERSAL FAILURE LOAD OF INSERT CONNECTIONS IN SANDWICH STRUCTURES

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ABSTRACT

The main objective of this work is to develop an analytical tool to predict failure loads of separable insert joints of sandwich structures. Insert connections provide several bonding interfaces to the honeycomb core as well as to the skin sheets, varying in number, position and size depending on the insert type. The idea is to improve these load paths on their quantity, quality and transferring load portions. With this paper the current status of this investigation is provided. Through-the-thickness insert connections are selected for experimental benchmark testing due to their high load-to-weight ratio. The first failure mode under transversal loads is shear buckling of the honeycomb core cell walls. This failure type is evaluated by a convenient applicable, semi-analytical equation, recommended by ECSS [1]. This formula is based on the “simple sandwich theory”, considering the design parameters core and skin sheet thickness, core shear strength, honeycomb cell size and insert radius in linear dependence. In contrast, the face sheet flexure stiffness as well as core density is not considered within the analytic equation, though their influence is not negligible. If significant tendencies of these non-considered parameters are deductible, the analytical approach could be extended. Therefore, analytical predictions are compared to benchmark test data taken from several sources. The analytical predictions show sufficient correspondence to the test data results, confirming the assumption of a linear dependency of the considered design parameters.

1 INTRODUCTION

Currently, many aerospace and ground traffic vehicles are built in fiber composite sandwich design. Sandwich structures provide a high flexure stiffness-to-weight ratio with a small demand of mostly very expansive, structural materials. Due to the core material, outstanding thermal and acoustic insulation are further advantages. However, mostly only small series space vehicles, racing cars and military ship vessels embody primary, load carrying sandwich structures. This may be caused by severe shortcomings of sandwich structures, e.g. complicated failure mechanisms, extensive manufacturing and the inability to bear local loads caused by the weak core and thin face sheets.

Sandwich elements embody face sheets consisting of high strength and dense structural material which are supported by a core made of lightweight material. Loads are carried mainly by the face sheets, converted into in-plane tensile- and compression stress. The core prevents the face sheets from sliding against each other as well as to converge, resulting in shear and anti-plane tension and compressive stress. Furthermore, the core stabilizes the compressed face sheet against buckling.

To fulfill requirements of assembly, maintenance, repair, function integration and automated mass production, sandwich structures need numerous separable connections, typically bolted connections. However, the core is not able to withstand high local clamping forces induced by screwed or riveted fasteners and has to be stabilized locally. Therefore multiple applications can be found in state-of-art sandwich structures (Fig. 1).

Figure 1: Applications to prevent the core from local crushing caused by screw prestress.

2 STATE OF THE ART OF SANDWICH INSERT CONNECTIONS

Special formed metallic or plastic core stabilizing elements, so-called “inserts”, offer an outstanding load-to-weight ratio. Besides supporting the core, inserts distribute the applied loads into the surrounding sandwich structure and if threaded act as counterpart for fasteners (Fig. 2).

Figure 2: Through-the-thickness insert type “NAS 1834”, stabilizing the core to resist bolt loads.

Design variables affecting the load carrying capability of sandwich insert connections are:

- **Face sheets:** Thickness $f_{1,2}$ and flexure stiffness $B_{y,f}$ (nominal: $b_{y,f}$) of the face sheets, taking the used fiber material and its stacking sequence into account.
- **Core:** Core height h_c , core density ρ_c , average shear strength $\tau_{W,min}$ of single walls in the honeycomb core cells and cell size S_c .
- **Insert system:** Radius b_i of the insert comprised in the effective potting radius b_p and the size of the undercut area of the potting under the face sheets.

Common insert types feature a wide range of different shapes and sandwich integration methods. The main characteristics are the position regarding the face sheet surfaces (recessed, flush, and protruding), the indentation depth of the insert (blind, through-the-thickness) and the potting compound (partial, fully, through-the-thickness) in the sandwich core as well as the number of bonding areas (Fig. 3, Fig. 4).

		Indentation depth of insert and potting compound in sandwich core		
		Partial potted	Fully potted	Through-the-thickness
Existence of flanges and position regarding the skins	Plane bonded flange, inner side			
	Flush, bearing bonded flange			
	Protruding, plane bonded flange			

Figure 3: Characteristics of insert types considering potting compound extend and flange positions.

Forces are initiated by the screw as well as the attachment contact area to the insert. Depending on the insert type, load portions are transferred by up to three load paths (Fig. 4). Caused by this load dispersion, insert connections are statically over-determined mechanical systems and thus difficult to be described analytically.

Figure 4: Distribution of loads in an insert connection by core and face sheet load paths.

3 STATE OF SCIENCE

ECSS [1] recommends the use of protruding, through-the-thickness inserts for high load connections in sandwich structures. This insert type provides an outstanding load carrying capability caused by its utilization of all three mentioned load paths (Fig. 4). Raghu et al. [2] examined the failure mechanisms and poor reliability of blind standard insert connections in FRP-skinned, honeycomb and foam core sandwich elements. Thomsen et al. [3] introduced an analytical description derived from the “higher order sandwich theory”. It allows predicting the local tension stresses of the skin to core contact area adjacent to the insert connection. Smith et al. [4] analyzed the load carrying capabilities of different insert types using the Thomsen formulae as well as the finite element method. Banerjee et al. [5] compared analytical results from the Thomson formulae to numerical results. Kress et al. [6] optimized the load carrying capability of bonded onsert flanges by adapting the shape of the flanges towards a homogeneous stress distribution. Block et al. [7] faced the problem of load introduction into sandwich elements with very thick cores. Here, common insert types show only low load carrying capabilities. To achieve bondings over the whole core thickness with a minimum amount of potting compound, slotted CFRP-tubes were developed, expanding in the borehole and generating an undercut under the face sheets. Extensive tests attested the competitiveness of these innovative insert types. Song et al. [8] used NAS 1834 type inserts in CFRP-skinned sandwich panels with aramid honeycomb core. Specimens, varying in core height and density as well as the staking sequence of the face sheets (affecting face sheet thickness e.g. flexure stiffness) were tested. The core density and the face sheet thickness were identified as design parameters with major influence on the load carrying capability. In contrast, the ECSS [1] showed fairly divergent results provided by an analytical sensitivity analysis based on the “simple sandwich theory”. Here, the potting radius and the core height exhibited the highest influences. The face sheet thickness was assumed to be negligible. This contradiction of results demands further investigations.

4 SELECTION OF INSERT TYPES

The contemplated load paths need to be investigated separately, starting with the core load path as content of this work. Thus, two insert types were identified using primarily the core load path with a minimal influence of the face sheet load paths. These inserts are the common type “NAS 1834” (Fig. 2, Fig. 5) and the non-standard type “Type 2” used for the lander structure “Philae” of the Rosetta mission (Fig. 5) [7].

Figure 5: Selected standard insert type NAS 1834 and nonstandard insert type Type 2.¹

¹ Pictures of insert “Type 2” by Block et al. [3].

5 DESCRIPTION OF INSERT LOAD DISTRIBUTION AND FAILURE MECHANISM

Within an insert connection featuring the insert type NAS 1834, the pull-out load P_{PO} is split in a major portion $P_{PO,c}$ carried by the honeycomb core as well as small load portions $P_{PO,f1}$ and $P_{PO,f2}$ bending the face sheets (Fig. 6) [7].

$$P_{PO} = P_{PO,c} + P_{PO,f1} + P_{PO,f2} \quad (1)$$

Figure 6: Pull-out load distribution onto surrounding sandwich structure in a through-the-thickness insert type NAS 1834 connection.

For sandwich connections featuring the selected insert types NAS 1834 and Type 2 the typical first failure is shear buckling of the single walls in the non-cut hexagonal cells adjacent to the potting-core interface (Fig. 8) [1]. The initial buckling is observable at the first maximum of the force-deflection curve, terminating the linear elastic range (Fig. 7). Initially reversible, the core shear deformation gets irreversible with further increasing force. Depending on the ratio of face sheet flexure stiffness to core shear stiffness, different load portions are carried by the remaining non-deformed cell walls as well as by the bended face sheet above the potting undercut until ultimate load. At ultimate failure level, the upper face sheet starts to peel of the core and the insert potting compound separates completely from the honeycomb core. At total failure level, insert and potting are pulled out of the sandwich.

Figure 7: Exemplary force-deflection graph for subjected insert types under transversal load.

6 ANALYTICAL PREDICTION OF THE FIRST FAILURE LOAD LEVEL

For an analytical prediction of the core load carrying capability of insert connections, ECSS [1] recommends an equation based on the “simple”, also called “antiplane” sandwich theory. In case of shear buckling of core walls to be the first failure, the failure prediction by this formula is assumed to be sufficiently accurate [1]. For this formula a homogeneous distribution of the core shear tension over the whole potting-to-core interface area A_P is assumed (Fig. 6).

$$P_{Po,c} = \tau_{c,typ} \cdot A_P = \tau_{c,typ} \cdot 2\pi \cdot b_P \cdot d \rightarrow \tau_{c,typ} = \frac{P_{Po,c}}{2\pi \cdot b_P \cdot d} \quad (2a)$$

The parameters utilized in equation (2a) are explained below. The effective average potting radius b_P is the mean value of all radial distances b_n from the insert center to the potting compound as well as to adjacent doubled honeycomb cell walls. The inclusion of these particular doubled cell walls is caused by their much higher stiffness compared to the single cell walls. Therefore they will not fail as first components. The doubled cell walls are originated in the manufacture procedure (Fig. 8). ECSS [1] provides an empirical based equation, taking the honeycomb cell size S_C , the insert radius b_i and if applied, a perforation of the cell walls into account.

$$b_P = \sum \frac{b_n}{n} = \begin{cases} 1,002064 \cdot b_i + 0,94035 \cdot S_C - 0,66151 & \text{for perforated cell walls} \\ b_i + 0,8 \cdot S_C & \text{for non - perforated cell walls} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

Figure 8: Single and doubled honeycomb core cell walls caused by expansion of honeycomb cells from flat, partly bonded strips. Parameters of the effective potting radius b_P .

The distance between the face sheet center lines is given by the sum of the core height h_c and the central axes of the face sheets (Fig. 6).

$$d = \frac{f_1}{2} + \frac{f_2}{2} + h_c \quad (4)$$

For the analytic load carrying capability prediction using equation (2a), ECSS [1] recommends to use the measured average shear strength of the core in W -direction, $\tau_{W,typ}$. Multiplied by a factor, taking the 72% greater number of single cell walls in L - than in W -direction into account, $\tau_{c,typ}$ results [1].

$$\tau_{c,typ} = \tau_{W,typ} \cdot 1,36 \quad (5)$$

7 REFERENCE TEST DATA

The test data were taken from Song et al. [8], Block et al. [7], [9] and the company Sell GmbH [10]. To minimize uncertainty factors, test data is only considered if the design parameters fulfill the following conditions (Table 1).

- CFRP or GFRP face sheets with quasi-isotropic properties in two normal directions.
- Aluminum or aramid honeycomb core material.
- A minimal volume of five test samples per set.

The test data design parameters provides a wide range of values and therefore they are grouped in four partitions. The effective potting radius values b_p are not partitioned due to the small range ($\Delta b_p = 28\%$) the selected test data provide (Table 1).

engineering constant	unit	partition				range (by percent)
		$\Delta 1$	$\Delta 2$	$\Delta 3$	$\Delta 4$	
b_i	[mm]		5,5 - 8,7			37%
b_p	[mm]		9,7 - 13,3			28%
$b_{y,f}$	[Nmm]	100	750	2500	20000	99,5%
d	[mm]	10	25	50	100	90%
E_f	[GPa]		31 - 72,5			57%
f_1, f_2	[mm]	0,3	0,5	1	1,5	83%
h_c	[mm]		9,6 - 100			90%
S_c	[mm]		3,2 - 6,4			50%
ρ_c	[kg/m ³]	25	49	80	128	80%
$\tau_{W,typ}$	[MPa]	0,35	0,96	1,4	2,5	86%

Table 1: Design parameter range of selected insert test samples.

8 COMPARISON OF ANALYTICAL AND TEST RESULTS

The deviations of the analytical prediction of equation (2a) from the test data are provided sorted considering different values of face sheet thicknesses f , nominal face sheet flexure stiffnesses $b_{y,f}$, honeycomb core shear strengths $\tau_{W,typ}$ and distances between the neutral axes of the face sheets d (Fig. 9 to Fig. 12). Shown are the individual ranges of each tested set (black), the deviation of the calculated predictions from the test results (blue) as well as the average deviations between calculated and experimental results of each partition (red). Objective is to deduct for which ranges of $f_{1,2}$, $b_{y,f}$, $\tau_{W,typ}$ and d equation (2a) provide acceptable compliance with the tests results and were there are too large deviations. With this knowledge, suitable parameter ranges for equation (2a) are deductible.

Apart from three exceptions (test sets BL-P03, -P07 and -P10), all of the predicted analytical pull-out failure load values are smaller than the test data results. The average deviation of all analytical to test data is - 19,5%. Therefore, equation (2a) is assumed to deliver too high, e.g. significantly conservative results within the addressed design parameter ranges.

The load portions transferred by the face sheet load paths $P_{PO,f1}$ and $P_{PO,f2}$ are expected to increase with thicker face sheets as deducted by Song et al. [8] (Fig. 6). The face sheet load paths are not included in equation (2a) and therefore the deviation of analytical and test data shall increase with thicker skin sheets. Figure 9 shows analytical predictions and test results ordered by the face sheet thicknesses f . No explicit trend is observable within the a face sheet thickness range of 0,25 - 1 mm due to a persistent deviation of analytical and test results (14 - 18%). However, face sheets with a thickness of 1,5 mm provide almost twice the deviation (30%) caused by the increasing load transfer towards the face sheets. Future investigations in test sets with thicker face sheets may confirm this trend.

Figure 9: Deviations of calculated failure load predictions from test results, partitioned into ranges of face sheet thickness f [7], [8], [9], [10].

Test sets with great differences between analytical prediction and test results (SO-P06=42%, SO-P07=51%) feature CFRP face sheets with high nominal face sheet flexure stiffnesses $b_{y,f}$. Nominal face sheet flexure stiffness values are given by equation (6) assuming identical top and bottom face sheets.

$$B_{y,f} = E_f \cdot I_f \rightarrow b_{y,f} = \frac{B_{y,f}}{b} = \frac{E_f \cdot I_f}{b} = \frac{E_f \cdot f_{1,2}^3}{12} \cdot \frac{b}{b} = \frac{E_f \cdot f_{1,2}^3}{12} \quad (6)$$

engineering constant	unit	property
b	[mm]	width of the sandwich panel or beam
$B_{y,f}$	[Nmm ²]	flexure stiffness e. g. bending stiffness of face sheets
$b_{y,f}$	[Nmm]	nominal flexure stiffness of face sheets
E_f	[N/mm ²]	average modulus of face sheets
I_f	[mm ⁴]	moment of inertia of face sheets

Table 2: Definition of dimensions for equation (6).

The results are shown in Figure 10. Here, considering the average deviations, no explicit trend is deductible for low $b_{y,f}$ within a range of 100 - 2500 Nmm. Additional, individual specimen with low $b_{y,f}$ also provides comparably high deviations (e.g. SE-P01 = 31% and SE-P04 = 26%) between test and analytical results. High $b_{y,f}$ (>20.000 Nmm) provide strongly increasing deviations, originated in the higher load portions carried by the face sheets instead of the core load path. Only the insufficient number of test sets with high face sheet flexure stiffnesses inhibits the deduction of an upper limit for equation (2a) considering high $b_{y,f}$.

Figure 10: Deviations of calculated failure load predictions from test results, partitioned into ranges of face sheet flexure stiffnesses $b_{y,f}$ [7], [8], [9], [10].

With increasing average core shear strength values in W -direction $\tau_{W,typ}$ the average deviations of analytical and test pull-out failure load values do not change significantly (Fig. 11). Therefore, the assumed linear influence of honeycomb core shear strength is considered to be correct [1]. Three test specimen sets with highest $\tau_{W,typ}$ (SE-P02, SE-P05, SO-P05) provide minimal differences between analytical and test results. Therefore, equation (2a) may work best with cores providing comparably high core shear stiffnesses. The comparison of analytical predictions and test results under consideration of the honeycomb core density ρ_c directly correlates to the core shear strength results. Therefore it is not commented additionally.

Figure 11: Deviations of calculated failure load predictions from test results, partitioned into ranges of core shear strength $\tau_{W,typ}$ [7], [8], [9], [10].

With increasing core thicknesses h_c (e. g. d), the average deviations are not changing significantly (Fig. 12). Therefore, no explicit trend is deductible, the assumption of linear dependency of equation (2a) is considered to be correct. Only very thick cores show a decrease of deviations. Here, future investigations in test sets with thicker cores may confirm this trend.

Figure 12: Deviations of calculated failure load predictions from test results, partitioned into ranges of distances between the face sheets neutral axes d [7], [8], [9], [10].

CONCLUSIONS

This work investigates a comparison between an analytical approach and test data considering the core load path of transversal loaded insert connections in sandwich structures with composite face sheets. Selected insert types, using primary the core load path as well as providing shear buckling of the honeycomb core as first failure mode were regarded. An equation given by ECSS [1] was applied, based on the “simple sandwich theory”, comprising face sheet and core thicknesses, effective potting radius and honeycomb core shear strength as design parameters in linear interdependence. The comparison of test data of different works shows sufficient conformity of results for insert-sandwich configurations with low face sheet flexure stiffnesses as well as high core shear strength and densities. For test sets with high face sheet thicknesses as well as high flexure stiffnesses, the ECSS equation is insufficient caused by the high portions of load transferred via the face sheets instead of the core, which is not considered within the equation. No definite tendency towards higher deviations between analytic prediction and tests results could be determined with alteration of the core thickness.

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